

The First Record of *Neoalticomerus formosus* Loew (Diptera: Odiniidae) from Ukraine

V. A. Korneyev

Kiev, Ukraine

valery.korneyev@gmail.com

A. V. Prokhorov

Kiev, Ukraine

al.val.prokhorov@gmail.com

The odiniid fly *Neoalticomerus formosus* Loew 1844, previously known to occur in Sweden, Finland, Germany, Poland, Latvia, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Switzerland, Austria, Hungary, Italy (Carles-Tolra, 2004), in the Leningrad Region of European Russia, Tyva Republic of Siberia, and Prymorsky Territory Far East Russia (Krivosheina, 1981; 1984), and Mongolia (Gaimari & Mathis, 2011) was collected in the West of Kyiv Region of Ukraine: Makariv District, 2.3 km SE of Bila Krynytsya village (50°37'32.45" N 29°29'46.40" E) on a bleeding oak together with numerous beetles and flies, 2 ♂, 15.06.2013 (Prokhorov leg) (SIZK). This is the first record of the genus *Neoalticomerus* Hendel, 1903 from Ukraine. By far, only *Odinia boletina* (Zetterstedt, 1848) (Korneyev, 1997) and *O. czernyi* Collin, 1952 (Korneyev, 2003) have been recorded from the city of Kiev.

Fig. 1. *Neoalticomerus formosus*, total view, dorsal.

Fig. 2. *N. formosus*, total view, left.

Carles-Tolra M. (2004). *Odiniidae*. Fauna Europaea, version 2.5, <http://www.faunaeur.org> (accessed 19.06.2013)

Gaimari, S. D. & Mathis, W. N. (2011). World catalogue and conspectus of the family Odiniidae (Diptera: Schizophora). *Myia*, 12, 291–339.

Korneyev, V. A. (1997). The first record of the family Odiniidae (Diptera, Acalyprata) from Ukraine. *Vestnik zoologii*, 31(4), 88.

Korneyev, V. A. (2003). The second species of the family Odiniidae (Diptera, Acalyprata) in Ukraine. *Vestnik zoologii*, 37(5), 68.

Krivosheina, N. P. (1981). On systematics and biology of the Palaearctic species of flies of the family Odiniidae (Diptera), entomophagous on xylophilic insects. In: *Insects destructors of the wood and their entomophages*, Moscow, A. N. Severtsov Institute of Evolutionary Morphology and Ecology, (1979), 130–157.

Krivosheina, N. P. (1984). Family Odiniidae. In: Soós, Á. & Papp, L. eds. *Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera*. Vol. 9. Micropezidae — Agromyzidae. Akadémiai Kiadó & Backhuis, Budapest & Amsterdam, 66–149.

Received 18.06.2013 Accepted 18.06.2013 Published 24.06.2013

© 2013 V. A. Korneyev & A. V. Prokhorov